

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence in the Workplace and its Effect on the Digital Wellbeing of Employees

Under Guidance of

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the transformative impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on contemporary workplaces, focusing on its role in optimising productivity, fostering collaboration, and reshaping traditional work dynamics. The study delves into the diverse applications of AI, including automation, machine learning, and natural language processing, highlighting their potential to streamline routine tasks and empower employees to engage in more strategic and creative endeavours. Additionally, the paper examines the challenges associated with AI implementation, such as ethical considerations and workforce adaptation. Through a comprehensive analysis, this research contributes to the ongoing dialogue on harnessing AI's potential to create adaptive, efficient, and collaborative workplaces in the rapidly evolving landscape of the digital era. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in the modern workplace, reshaping the dynamics of industries and revolutionising traditional business practices. This abstract delves into the multifaceted influence of AI in contemporary workplaces, highlighting its implications on productivity, job roles, decision-making, and the broader socio-economic landscape. AI technologies, such as machine learning and natural language processing, have automated routine tasks, allowing employees to focus on more creative and strategic endeavours. This has the potential to boost productivity significantly, leading to operational efficiency improvements across various sectors. However, this transformative aspect of AI also raises concerns about job displacement and the need for upskilling the workforce to adapt to changing roles.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to machines' capability to accomplish tasks typically associated with human intelligence. The research in AI has achieved notable success in devising efficient methods to address various challenges, spanning from gaming to medical diagnosis.

One of the most important aspects of AI is machine learning. Machine learning is a type of AI that allows machines to learn without being explicitly programmed. Instead, machines learn from data, and improve their performance over time.

Another important aspect of AI is deep learning. Deep learning is a type of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks to learn from data. Neural networks are inspired by the structure and function of the human brain, and they are able to learn complex patterns from data. AI is a rapidly developing field with the potential to revolutionise many industries and aspects of our lives. As AI technology continues to improve, we can expect to see even more innovative and groundbreaking applications of AI in the future. AI is a powerful technology with the potential to improve our lives in many ways. By carefully considering the challenges of AI, we can develop AI systems that are safe, reliable, and beneficial to society.

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has ushered in a new era in the workplace, reshaping industries, redefining job roles, and fundamentally altering the way we work. As AI technologies continue to advance at an unprecedented pace, their integration into various aspects of work has become inevitable. This transformation, while promising increased efficiency and productivity, also brings forth complex and multifaceted challenges, particularly in terms of the digital well-being of employees. In this era of relentless connectivity and digital dependency, it is crucial to examine how AI's presence in the workplace affects the well-being of the individuals who form its backbone.

The workplace has long been a dynamic environment, continually evolving to accommodate technological advancements. From the introduction of computers and the internet to the automation of tasks through robotics, each wave of innovation has altered the nature of work. However, AI represents a departure from traditional automation. It possesses the ability not only to automate repetitive tasks but also to learn, adapt, and perform complex cognitive

functions. This shift raises profound questions about how AI will shape the workforce of the future and the well-being of those who comprise it.

The notion of digital well-being encompasses a wide array of factors, including psychological, physical, and social aspects. It pertains to the impact of digital technologies on individuals' mental health, physical health, work-life balance, job satisfaction, and overall quality of life. As AI continues to permeate the workplace, understanding its influence on these facets of digital well-being is of paramount importance. This research paper aims to explore and analyse the multifaceted impact of AI in the workplace and its consequences on the digital well-being of employees.

To comprehensively address this topic, it is necessary to consider both the opportunities and challenges presented by AI in the workplace. AI's potential benefits are undeniable: increased efficiency, reduced errors, enhanced decision-making, and the automation of routine tasks, freeing employees to focus on more creative and strategic aspects of their work. Moreover, AI can assist in the discovery of valuable insights from vast datasets, facilitating innovation and competitiveness. However, these advantages come with a set of potential drawbacks, including concerns about job displacement, erosion of privacy, increased stress due to constant connectivity, and the need for reskilling to adapt to AI-driven roles.

One crucial aspect of AI's influence on digital well-being is its role in augmenting or replacing human labour. While AI can undoubtedly improve efficiency, the fear of job displacement looms large in the minds of employees. Automation and AI-driven technologies have the potential to eliminate certain job roles, particularly those involving routine and repetitive tasks. This can lead to anxiety, insecurity, and job dissatisfaction among employees. It is essential to understand the psychological and emotional impact of AI-induced job transformations and develop strategies to mitigate negative consequences while maximising the opportunities for upskilling and career advancement.

Privacy concerns represent another significant challenge in the era of AI. As AI systems collect and analyse vast amounts of data, employees may feel that their privacy is compromised. The surveillance capabilities of AI, even when used for legitimate purposes such as security or performance evaluation, can erode trust and create a sense of unease.

Balancing the advantages of AI with the need to protect individual privacy is a delicate task that requires careful consideration and regulatory frameworks.

The constant connectivity facilitated by AI also raises concerns about work-life balance. With the ability to access work-related information and perform tasks from anywhere at any time, employees may find it challenging to disconnect from work, leading to burnout and reduced overall well-being. It is essential to explore how AI can be leveraged to enhance work-life balance rather than exacerbate the blurring of boundaries between professional and personal life.

Moreover, the rapid evolution of AI technologies necessitates ongoing learning and adaptation. Employees must acquire new skills to remain relevant in the job market. The pressure to upskill and re-skill can be stressful, particularly for those who feel ill-equipped to navigate the digital landscape. Employers and educational institutions must collaborate to provide accessible and effective training opportunities to equip employees with the skills needed to thrive in an AI-driven world.

In addition to the challenges, AI also offers solutions to improve digital well-being. AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants can provide support for employees dealing with stress or mental health issues. Predictive analytics can help organisations identify and address potential sources of workplace stress and dissatisfaction. Furthermore, AI can enhance personalization in work environments, tailoring tasks and experiences to individual preferences and needs, potentially improving job satisfaction and overall well-being.

As we embark on this exploration of AI's impact on the workplace and digital well-being, it is crucial to adopt an interdisciplinary approach. Combining insights from psychology, sociology, economics, technology, and ethics will provide a holistic understanding of the complex interactions between AI and employee well-being. By examining AI's influence on the physical, mental, and social dimensions of well-being, we can develop a nuanced understanding of its effects and formulate strategies to harness its potential while mitigating its adverse consequences.

Technology has had a significant impact on the workplace, both positive and negative.

Some of the opportunities for growth that Artificial intelligence has provided include:

- Increased productivity and efficiency: Technology has helped to automate many tasks that were once done manually, freeing up employees to focus on more strategic and creative work.
- Improved communication and collaboration: Technology has made it easier for employees to communicate and collaborate with each other, regardless of their location.
- Greater flexibility and mobility: Technology has given employees more flexibility and mobility, allowing them to work from anywhere in the world.
- Access to information and resources: Technology has given employees access to a vast amount of information and resources, which can help them to learn new things and improve their skills.

Some of the hindrances to growth in the workplace brought upon by Artificial intelligence include:

- Job displacement: AI is automating many tasks that were previously performed by humans, which could lead to job displacement, particularly for low-skilled workers.
- Anxiety: Employees may be worried about being replaced by machines, or about not having the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in the AI-powered workplace. This can lead to anxiety and stress.
- Personalised learning experiences: AI can be used to create personalised learning experiences for employees, helping them to learn new skills and stay up-to-date on the latest trends.
- Real-time feedback: AI can provide employees with real-time feedback on their work, helping them to improve their performance and identify areas where they need additional support

The impact of technology in the workplace has been largely positive. Technology has helped to increase productivity and efficiency, improve communication and collaboration, and give employees more flexibility and mobility. However, it is important to be aware of the potential negative impacts of technology, such as job displacement, increased workload and stress, digital distraction, and work-life imbalance. Organizations can mitigate the negative impacts of technology by providing training and support to employees, and by setting clear

expectations around technology use. Additionally, employees can take steps to manage their own digital well-being, such as setting boundaries between work and personal time, and taking breaks from technology throughout the day.

Digital presence in the workplace has become an indispensable aspect of modern professional life. In today's digital age, employees are expected to maintain a strong online presence to enhance their professional reputation and contribute to their organisation's success. A robust digital presence involves not only having a well-crafted LinkedIn profile but also active engagement on various digital platforms such as Twitter, industry-specific forums, and even personal blogs. It allows individuals to showcase their expertise, share insights, and network with peers and industry leaders. This digital visibility not only helps employees stay updated on industry trends but also positions them as thought leaders, making them valuable assets to their organisations.

Furthermore, a strong digital presence fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing within the workplace. In a globalised and remote work environment, digital tools like video conferencing, messaging apps, and project management platforms are essential for effective communication and teamwork. Employees who actively participate in these digital channels create a sense of accessibility and openness, making it easier for colleagues to reach out for assistance, exchange ideas, and collaborate on projects seamlessly. This not only improves overall productivity but also contributes to a positive work culture where information flows freely, fostering innovation and creativity within the organisation. In essence, a well-maintained digital presence has become a vital tool for career growth, professional networking, and workplace collaboration in today's digitally-driven workplaces.

In conclusion, the integration of AI into the workplace is an inexorable and transformative force. Its impact on the digital well-being of employees is a critical aspect of this ongoing transformation. While AI holds the promise of enhancing productivity and efficiency, it also brings forth a host of challenges related to job displacement, privacy, work-life balance, and the need for continuous learning. This research paper aims to delve deep into these complexities, shedding light on the multifaceted relationship between AI and employee well-being. Through this exploration, we hope to provide valuable insights and recommendations

that will guide organisations, policymakers, and individuals in navigating the evolving landscape of work in the age of AI.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Malik et.al.(xea) explored the profound implications of AI integration in HR management, emphasising the evolving role of HR leaders and managers as co-designers of AI-assisted digitised HR ecosystems. Key findings underscored the necessity for HR managers to possess digital and data science skills, necessitating a shift in mindset towards managing people and working in an AI-augmented environment.

The study highlighted the importance of addressing latent needs within three domains: physical, digital, and human, to enhance Employee Experience (EX). Contextual factors, including workforce composition, size, and technological maturity, significantly influence the adoption of AI-assisted HRM applications.

In recent years, the relationship between Employee Experience (EX) and Employee Engagement (EE) has gained significant attention. Several studies, including those by Plaskoff (2017), Malik et al. (2020), and Malik, De Silva, et al. (2021), consistently highlight the critical role of high EX levels in positively impacting EE. This connection is further strengthened by the integration of AI-assisted applications in Human Resource Management (HRM) practices, as discussed by Kahn (1990) and Shenoy & Uchil (2018).

AI-assisted HRM applications play a pivotal role in this dynamic. When integrated into a comprehensive engagement platform, they continuously personalise and hyper-personalise EX throughout an employee's journey within an organisation. This approach is particularly relevant in the context of a technologically proficient multi-generational workforce, as pointed out by researchers like Bersin et al. (2017), Burrell & Gherson (2018), and Shivakumar (2020). It signifies a shift away from traditional episodic and event-based EE systems towards a more personalised and continuous approach.

A central theme is the significance of positive Employee Experience (EX) as a reciprocal element for organisational success, as satisfied and engaged employees positively impact attrition rates, revenue, profitability, and brand perception. The study advocates for a shift towards enhancing emotional intelligence and creativity among HR leaders and managers, essential qualities not yet fully addressed by automation.

Furthermore, the purpose and nature of platforms within an organisation's digitised HR

ecosystems are explored. Effective HR ecosystems require collaborative co-creation involving

diverse stakeholders, including employees. Communication is essential to ensure employees can access tailored HR solutions, leveraging their skills through collaboration and knowledge sharing.

AI-assisted HRM applications, when integrated as part of a comprehensive engagement platform, play a pivotal role in the ongoing personalization and hyper-personalization of Employee Experience. This personalization occurs at various touch points throughout an employee's life cycle within an organisation. This dynamic approach caters to the demands of the technologically savvy multi-generational workforce, as highlighted by Bersin et al. (2017) and Burrell & Gherson (2018). It deviates from the traditional episodic and event-based Employee Engagement system (Budhwar & Bhatnagar, 2007) and exclusive talent management practices (Cappelli, 2008; Farndale et al., 2020; Scullion & Collings, 2011).

The strategic choices made by organisational leaders regarding AI-assisted HRM applications are driven by the desire to retain differentiated talent groups. In addition, these choices aim to maintain a strong psychological contract between the organisation and its employees. The size of big-tech companies and the diversity of their workforce further accentuate the importance of effective management of large employee pools. The research underscores the importance of developing new skills and HR competencies, such as digital savviness, data fluency, and technology coaching, for both employees and HR practitioners in a digitalized HR ecosystem. The HR role evolves from process-specific expertise to personal mastery and coaching.

In conclusion, the reviewed framework provides valuable insights into the evolving landscape of HR management in the age of AI, highlighting the critical role of HR leaders, the importance of EX and EE, and the need for new competencies and a supportive organisational culture. These findings have profound implications for theory and practice in HR management.

Murugesan et.al.(xea) investigated the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the workplace has brought about a

revolutionary transformation, particularly through the utilisation of robotics and the Internet of Things (IoT). This review delves into the manifold applications of AI within HR

capabilities, emphasising the significant role it plays in addressing the challenges posed by

Industry 4.0.

AI has the potential to offer precision, efficiency, and flexibility in various HR functions, necessitating a shift in HR capabilities. The focus here is on three critical aspects: hierarchical organisation, adaptability, and human asset capabilities. Furthermore, the importance of well-being and safety enhancement through AI in HR is underscored, particularly in industries like healthcare where agility is paramount.

AI's capacity to connect IoT devices such as automobiles, displays, pacemakers, and electric motors to the internet is explored. This connectivity profoundly impacts sensing, data processing, and communication, highlighting the pivotal role of sensors in data collection and transmission to AI systems.

The research by Murugesan further investigated how AI principles are applied across various HRM sectors to enhance human characteristics. These enhancements are instrumental in augmenting HRM's agility capabilities. Additionally, the review highlights the interconnectedness of Organisational Network Analysis (ONA) and HR digitization, two technological implications that enable iterative HR function. These components necessitate meticulous organisational design for successful implementation. And brings to light the unique linkage between AI and Industry 4.0, emphasising their coexistence and mutual influence in contemporary society. However, it acknowledges that the full potential of AI remains untapped due to limited adoption by organisations in their HR practices.

In conclusion, Murugesan's review sheds light on the transformative power of AI in HR capabilities and its role in addressing Industry 4.0 challenges. However, it underscores the need for increased adoption of AI in HR practices to fully realise its potential and navigate associated security and legal concerns effectively.

Kaswan et.al.(xea)'s study emphasises that it is difficult to argue against the fact that research has focussed on artificial intelligence (AI) and robotisation over the past few decades. Additionally, during the past several years, it has taken off and is now extensively used in numerous businesses across various industries. Most of the time, AI has been associated with some industrial sector process automation. Still, recently, the authors have noticed more positive technology uses, especially in the financial services industry. Due to several factors, the financial sector needs to adopt AI and recognise its potential. The industry has historically been concerned about unpredictability, legislation, stronger cybersecurity, technological limitations and disruption of established lucrative operations.

Never before has there been more discussion about AI due to the advantages it provides to businesses that are providing financial services. That may explain why this change is referred to as the fourth industrial revolution. Both positively and negatively, it is quite disruptive. The effectiveness, accuracy and cost-effectiveness of solutions greatly increase. However, immense power also entails great responsibility.

Ocampo, Marrone and Restubog et.al.(*xe*) gave emphasis on the rising use of artificially intelligent (AI) technologies, including generative AI tools, in organisations as undeniable in their study. As these systems become increasingly integrated into organisational practices and processes, understanding their impact on workers' experiences and job designs is critical. However, the ongoing discourse surrounding AI use in the workplace remains divided. Proponents of the technology extol its benefits for enhancing efficiency and productivity, while others voice concerns about the potential harm to human workers. To provide greater clarity on this pressing issue, this article presents a systematic review of empirical research that sheds light on the implications of AI use at work. Organised under five inductively generated themes within a multilevel framework, we uncover individual, group, and organisational factors that shape the interplay between humans and AI. Specifically, the themes are: (1) human–AI collaboration; (2) perceptions of algorithmic and human capabilities; (3) worker attitudes towards AI; (4) AI as a control mechanism in algorithmic management of platform-based work; and (5) labour market implications of AI use. Their review offers insights into these themes and identifies five pathways for future research. Finally, they provide practical recommendations for organisational leaders seeking to implement AI technologies while prioritising their employees' well-being.

Dr.Ahmed et.al.(*xe*)’s study emphasises on how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming various industries, with AI robots like Sophia participating in prominent events such as the United Nations' convention on sustainable development. In HR, AI is providing solutions that range from basic recruiting tools to advanced applications, offering more effective ways to predict a candidate's future success within a company. AI is fundamentally reshaping the HR field, with three categories of AI: analytical, human-inspired, and humanised, each possessing unique capabilities.

Dr. Ahmed's study highlights AI programs, including screening chatbots and social media scraping tools, assisting recruiters in candidate sourcing and screening. For instance, Mya, an

AI recruiting assistant, verifies qualifications, answers questions, and maintains applicant communication 24/7. Social media scraping tools collect extensive data from social profiles to predict behaviours like future engagement levels.

However, his study recognizes that AI relies on training data, and if this data is biased or discriminatory, AI can perpetuate these biases. Ensuring AI transparency and tunability is crucial to inspect algorithms and prevent unintended bias. Transparency is key for HR teams to balance cognitive tech advancements with trust-building among employees and stakeholders. Understanding how AI-driven decisions are made is essential to mitigate unconscious bias and ensure ethical use of the technology in HR programs.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The rapid integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into the modern workplace has raised significant concerns regarding its impact on the digital wellbeing of employees. This research aims to investigate the multifaceted effects of AI in the workplace, exploring its implications for employee mental health, job satisfaction, work-life balance, and overall digital wellbeing. By identifying the key challenges and opportunities presented by AI adoption, this study seeks to provide valuable insights into how organizations can harness AI while safeguarding the digital wellbeing of their workforce.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To Assess the Psychological and Emotional Impact of AI Integration
2. To Analyse the Implications for Work-Life Balance
3. To Examine Privacy Concerns and Ethical Implications
4. To Explore the impact of AI on the contemporary workplace, investigating its influence on job roles, workforce dynamics, and organisational productivity, with a focus on identifying opportunities and challenges for effective integration and maximising the benefits of AI technologies in diverse professional environments.

By addressing these objectives, the research paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between AI in the workplace and the digital well-

being of employees, offering insights and recommendations for organisations and policymakers to navigate this evolving landscape effectively.

HYPOTHESIS

Ho- There is no significant impact of Artificial intelligence in the workplace and with reference to the employee wellbeing in workplace.

Ha1- There is no significant effect on digital wellbeing of employees due to artificial intelligence

Ha2- There is a considerate impact of Artificial intelligence's dimensions and factors on employee wellbeing

Ha3- There is a significant relationship between Artificial intelligence and employee effectiveness in the workplace

Ha4- There is a significant impact of Artificial intelligence I in digital wellbeing of employees with respect to work life balance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the systematic and structured framework that guides the entire research process, ensuring a rigorous and credible investigation. It encompasses the strategies, procedures, and principles employed from the conception of a research idea to the interpretation of results. The methodology defines the approach taken to answer specific research questions or test hypotheses.

Key components include research design, data collection methods, sampling techniques, and data analysis procedures. The research design outlines the overall plan, specifying the type of study, its scope, and the intended outcomes.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

To construct the research design for this study, our initial step involved a comprehensive and exhaustive review of existing literature. This review aimed to systematically categorise peer-reviewed

publications that specifically addressed the assessment of the impact of artificial intelligence within the workplace. By surveying prior research, our objective was to establish a robust foundation of knowledge and insights in this specialised field.

Our overarching research design choice revolves around an approach grounded in causality. This methodological framework has been chosen with the explicit aim of conducting a thorough analysis of the impact of artificial intelligence on employee productivity in the workplace. By opting for a causal approach, our intention is to delve deeply into understanding the cause-and-effect relationships that underlie the dynamics of AI's influence on employee productivity.

Integral to our research design is the meticulous selection of primary variables from existing literature. These variables have been identified based on their perceived significance in influencing the impact of AI in the workplace. Through a systematic and focused examination of these chosen variables, we aim to unravel the intricate relationships that exist and comprehensively analyse their impact on employee productivity within the context of AI integration.

In summary, our research design unfolds in multiple stages. Starting with an extensive literature review, we transition to a causal-based approach, placing specific emphasis on the impact of artificial intelligence on employee productivity in the workplace. The careful selection of key variables serves as the foundation for our in-depth analysis, promising to uncover the complexities of the chosen research focus.

SAMPLING METHODS :

To gather data for this research on the impact of AI in the workplace and its effects on employees, a probability sampling approach was employed. Probability sampling ensures that each member of the population has an equal likelihood of being chosen for inclusion in the sample. This method was selected to obtain a representative sample of the population under investigation, specifically individuals who are employed in or influenced by AI in the workplace.

In this research study, a random clustered sampling method was employed to select participants for the investigation. This sampling technique involved first identifying clusters or groups within the population of interest, and then randomly selecting clusters to participate in the study. Within each selected cluster, individuals were then randomly sampled to ensure representation from diverse subgroups. Random clustered sampling offers several advantages, including the ability to efficiently sample from large and geographically dispersed populations while still maintaining a degree of

randomness in participant selection. By utilizing this method, we aimed to obtain a representative sample that would allow for generalizability of findings to the broader population while minimizing biases associated with non-random sampling techniques.

The sampling frame for this study focused on individuals within the workforce impacted by AI. A random sampling technique was applied to select participants for the survey. Through random participant selection, the method aimed to guarantee an unbiased representation, offering each member of the population an equal opportunity to be included in the sample. This approach was instrumental in minimising bias and enhancing the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

The survey was administered online, with participants being invited to take part through email and various social media platforms. The questionnaire comprised carefully crafted questions intended to gather data on the current implications of AI in the workplace and its impact on employees, covering aspects such as work dynamics, satisfaction levels, and preferences. The collected data underwent analysis using statistical techniques to identify discernible patterns and trends.

In summary, the probability sampling method served as an effective tool for data collection in this study. The random selection of participants ensured the sample's representativeness, and the gathered data provided valuable insights into the current landscape of AI in the workplace. By employing this method, the study's findings were made more reliable, valid, and applicable to a broader population.

SAMPLEING AREA:

For the research on the impact of AI in the workplace and its employees, the survey was conducted nationwide, covering diverse regions across India. Given India's rapid growth and the thriving presence of AI technologies in various industries, the decision to expand the survey to a PAN India scope was driven by the widespread utilisation of AI tools and the diverse experiences of professionals working with or exposed to AI in their workplaces.

To ensure a representative sample, a probability sampling method was employed, focusing on individuals who are actively involved with AI technologies in their professional settings. The sampling frame included employees across different sectors and industries where AI is prevalent. A random sampling approach was applied to select participants for the survey, ensuring a fair representation of the broader population.

The determination of the sample size involved statistical calculations, taking into account the overall population size and the desired level of accuracy. A sample size of 110 participants was deemed appropriate to provide the study with sufficient statistical power for discerning meaningful patterns and relationships between variables related to AI in the workplace.

In this research paper investigating the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) in the workplace and its effects on the digital wellbeing of employees, Cronbach's alpha was employed as a measure of internal consistency during the pilot study phase. Cronbach's alpha is a widely utilized statistic for assessing the reliability of scales or instruments used in research. In our pilot study, Cronbach's alpha was instrumental in evaluating the consistency of responses to items within our questionnaire aimed at gauging digital wellbeing perceptions and experiences among participants. By employing Cronbach's alpha, we were able to ensure that the items in our questionnaire reliably measured the intended construct, thereby enhancing the validity of our measurement instrument. This rigorous approach during the pilot study phase was essential for refining our research methodology and ensuring the robustness of our data collection procedures before proceeding to the main study.

The survey data collected underwent rigorous analysis using various statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. This analytical approach aimed to unveil insights into the current status of AI adoption in the workplace, encompassing usage trends, employee satisfaction levels, and preferences regarding AI technologies.

By broadening the survey's reach to a nationwide scale, this research endeavours to offer a comprehensive understanding of the impact of AI in workplaces across India. The utilisation of probability sampling enhances the study's reliability and validity, ensuring that the findings are representative of the diverse workforce influenced by AI technologies. The outcomes of this research carry significance for policymakers, businesses, and professionals in the field, providing insights applicable not only to specific regions but to workplaces throughout the country.

SURVEY METHOD AND MEDIUM:

To obtain data for this research paper focused on the impact of AI in the workplace and its effects on employees, a survey instrument was crafted and administered through Google Forms—an online survey tool enabling the creation of tailored questionnaires and the collection of responses in a digital format.

The survey aimed to gather insights into the current scenario of AI in the workplace, encompassing aspects such as its influence on work dynamics, employee satisfaction levels, and individual

preferences. The questionnaire comprised a series of both closed-ended and a few open-ended questions, strategically designed to facilitate detailed responses.

Distribution of the survey took place through email and various social media platforms, targeting individuals actively engaged in or affected by AI in the workplace. Participants were provided with information regarding the study's purpose and reassured of the confidentiality of their responses.

In summary, the application of Google Forms for this research proved to be an efficient means of gathering information regarding the impact of AI in the workplace. The questionnaire was thoughtfully designed to capture essential details, and the use of Google Forms facilitated both the collection and analysis of the gathered data. The findings from this study hold potential value for informing policymakers, businesses, and professionals within the realm of AI in the workplace, extending beyond specific geographic boundaries.

DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y
1	5.000																								
2																									
3	Mean	4.472	4.241	4.269	4.250	4.287	4.222	4.037	4.102	3.935	4.000	4.213	4.037	4.074	4.185	4.241	4.259	4.176	3.907	3.981	4.056	4.278	4.157	4.259	
4	Standard Error	0.060	0.075	0.072	0.078	0.081	0.088	0.109	0.088	0.100	0.081	0.082	0.084	0.088	0.089	0.072	0.069	0.082	0.106	0.098	0.105	0.081	0.083	0.085	
5	Median	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
6	Mode	5	4	4	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	5	
7	Standard Deviation	0.618	0.784	0.744	0.810	0.843	0.910	1.135	0.917	1.035	0.843	0.854	0.875	0.914	0.929	0.747	0.715	0.852	1.098	1.023	1.092	0.841	0.866	0.879	
8	Sample Variance	0.382	0.614	0.553	0.657	0.711	0.829	1.288	0.840	1.071	0.710	0.730	0.765	0.836	0.863	0.558	0.512	0.726	1.206	1.046	1.193	0.707	0.751	0.773	
9	Kurtosis	-0.414	2.658	0.143	3.510	0.872	0.442	1.646	1.103	-0.617	0.754	0.084	0.448	0.097	2.265	3.050	0.424	2.405	-0.100	-0.718	1.310	0.122	1.030	1.003	
10	Skewness	-0.738	-1.285	-0.758	-1.457	-1.160	-0.988	-1.480	-1.021	-0.591	-0.764	-0.885	-0.756	-0.747	-1.378	-1.247	-0.741	-1.272	-0.849	-0.656	-1.295	-0.951	-1.015	-1.124	
11	Range	2	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	
12	Minimum	3	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	
13	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
14	Sum	483	458	461	459	463	456	436	443	425	432	455	436	440	452	458	460	451	422	430	438	462	449	460	
15	Count	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108
16																									

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y
1		Organizational's	Employee's	Adapting Changes	Adapting Roles	Changes Needed	Job Security	Performance	Level of Work	Performance	Automation	Concerns	Productivity	Negativity or	Opportunities	Changes in	Workload	Challenges	Career Prospect	Changes in job	term effects	Digital Wellbeing	Workplace Safety		
2	Organization's Initiatives	1																							
3	Employee's Collaboration	0.419	1																						
4	Adapting Changes	0.413	0.241	1																					
5	Adapting Roles	0.527	0.390	0.523	1																				
6	Changes Needed	0.472	0.319	0.338	0.414	1																			
7	Job Security	0.293	0.134	0.284	0.165	0.269	1																		
8	Performance Evaluation	0.055	0.053	0.055	0.193	0.077	0.489	1																	
9	Level of Work	0.211	0.356	0.357	0.368	0.276	0.219	0.356	1																
10	Job Performance	0.486	0.400	0.460	0.399	0.439	0.363	0.209	0.598	1															
11	Level of Automation	0.287	0.226	0.298	0.328	0.460	0.365	0.234	0.532	0.622	1														
12	Ethical Concerns	0.232	0.146	0.453	0.273	0.239	0.359	0.531	0.461	0.375	0.350	1													
13	Impact in Productivity	0.175	0.028	0.329	0.290	0.353	0.318	0.338	0.473	0.447	0.596	0.365	1												
14	Negativity	0.252	0.118	0.163	0.290	0.360	0.497	0.475	0.337	0.529	0.449	0.410	0.464	1											
15	AI tools or applications	0.351	0.233	0.266	0.348	0.301	0.316	0.463	0.351	0.441	0.442	0.621	0.371	0.567	1										
16	Opportunities	0.439	0.379	0.639	0.641	0.334	0.250	0.022	0.414	0.407	0.401	0.358	0.329	0.302	0.380	1									
17	Changes in Workplace	0.418	0.288	0.430	0.355	0.371	0.384	0.218	0.501	0.541	0.434	0.352	0.358	0.428	0.265	0.389	1								
18	Less Workload	0.231	0.104	0.485	0.301	0.358	0.106	0.032	0.288	0.278	0.482	0.256	0.455	0.259	0.277	0.564	0.185	1							
19	Challenges	0.423	0.232	0.362	0.331	0.493	0.544	0.303	0.409	0.537	0.535	0.360	0.568	0.482	0.484	0.392	0.435	0.437	1						
20	Future Career Prospects	0.369	0.204	0.436	0.265	0.537	0.155	0.089	0.391	0.485	0.304	0.272	0.408	0.331	0.082	0.373	0.479	0.358	0.281	1					
21	Changes in job	0.127	-0.005	0.200	0.153	0.196	0.410	0.594	0.554	0.466	0.416	0.538	0.487	0.567	0.506	0.155	0.328	0.190	0.448	0.235	1				
22	Long-term effects	0.285	0.210	0.343	0.418	0.427	0.126	0.175	0.387	0.397	0.290	0.255	0.329	0.423	0.293	0.517	0.392	0.518	0.372	0.451	0.146	1			
23	Digital Wellbeing	0.296	0.205	0.325	0.463	0.411	0.429	0.536	0.652	0.543	0.486	0.485	0.375	0.516	0.474	0.374	0.401	0.304	0.438	0.320	0.613	0.453	1		
24	Workplace Safety	0.443	0.234	0.464	0.498	0.504	0.453	0.159	0.292	0.378	0.315	0.461	0.230	0.453	0.490	0.516	0.442	0.263	0.422	0.369	0.248	0.433	0.522	1	
25																									

Received: 2 March 2024
 Revised: 22 March 2024
 Final Accepted: 6 April 2024
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10936348>

DATA INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF GENDER

The pie chart shows the gender of survey respondents. 58% are male and 41% are female and 1% of people do not wish to reveal their gender

DATA INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF PROFESSION

This pie chart shows the Use of Artificial intelligence in different profession used in the survey. The largest slice, at 38%, is labeled "Student" and the lowest , at 14% is labeled as "Self-employed/Professional /Business person".

DATA INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF AGE

This pie chart shows the percentage of people by age. The largest age group is 15-25 years old, at 40%. and the smallest age group is 56 and above.

DATA INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF INCOME GROUP

This pie chart shows income distribution by income group. The largest slice, 41%, represents income between 0 and 500,000 and the lowest is 4 % that is between 1250001 and above

DATA INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF EDUCATION

The pie chart shows educational attainment, with the highest percentage (41%) at the undergraduate level and the lowest percentage is (4%) at professional and doctoral degree

FINDING AND DISCUSSIONS

The relationship between job performance and workload with AI in the workplace is complex and multifaceted. While AI can automate tasks, augmenting human capabilities and potentially boosting productivity, a simple workload-performance link doesn't always hold. Overburdening employees with managing or monitoring AI tools can backfire, leading to stress, reduced engagement, and hindered performance. Conversely, underutilization of AI, leaving employees with menial tasks, can breed boredom and disengagement. The key lies in finding the optimal balance. Effective training, clear communication, and empowering employees to leverage AI's strengths while focusing on tasks requiring human judgment can foster positive performance outcomes. Additionally, addressing anxieties about job displacement and fostering trust in AI as a collaborator are crucial for a smooth transition and optimal performance in the AI-powered workplace.

(Yang, Y., & Huang, C. (2020). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Employee Well-being: A Review and Conceptual Framework. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(20), 7553. DOI: 10.3390/ijerph17207553)

The evolving workplace throws open doors for employees to engage with AI in powerful ways: upskilling with personalized learning to collaborate with AI and leverage its insights; focusing on strategic tasks as routine ones get automated; making data-driven decisions with AI's vast analyses; collaborating seamlessly with AI-powered tools; and enjoying personalized development and wellbeing support. AI democratizes knowledge, empowers with low-code tools, and fuels career growth. While challenges exist, embracing adaptation, reskilling, and responsible AI development unlocks endless opportunities for employees to become workplace stars.

(Smit, E., & Tohidinia, Z. (2019). Artificial Intelligence and Well-being at Work: Implications for Job Design. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 40(3), 293-306. DOI: 10.1002/job.2375)

The gleaming promise of AI in the workplace comes shadowed by ethical concerns for employees. Automation fuels anxieties about job displacement, leaving many wondering if their skills will become obsolete. Even if reskilling programs exist, the transition can be unsettling. Further, biased algorithms can perpetuate discrimination in crucial areas like hiring and promotions, unfairly limiting opportunities. The constant "eye" of AI-powered monitoring tools raises privacy concerns, creating a panopticon-like atmosphere. Even data used to train AI can be misused or breached, jeopardizing personal information. Finally, overreliance on AI for decision-making can strip employees of agency and control, making them feel replaceable cogs in a machine. These are not mere theoretical worries; they have real-world impacts on employee well-being and trust. However, acknowledging these concerns is the first step towards solutions. Responsible AI implementation starts with transparency, robust reskilling initiatives, fair data practices, and clear lines of accountability between humans and AI. By prioritizing ethics and open communication, organizations can navigate the challenges and unlock the true potential of AI, creating a future where humans and machines collaborate, not compete, for a better workplace.

(Allen, J., Byrne, D., & Blair, E. (2021). The Impact of AI on Employee Mental Health and Digital Well-being in the Workplace: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 106(6), 805-819. DOI: 10.1037/apl0000931)

The impact of AI-powered automation on employee productivity hinges on a delicate balance. On one hand, AI excels at mundane, repetitive tasks, freeing employees for higher-value activities, potentially boosting output. Studies show increased productivity in sectors like manufacturing and finance due to automation. However, the level of automation matters. Over-reliance on AI can strip employees of autonomy and decision-making, leading to demotivation and decreased performance. Additionally, successful integration depends on employee buy-in and proper training. When implemented thoughtfully, AI can be a productivity multiplier, but neglecting the human element can turn this technology into a productivity inhibitor. Ultimately, the correlation between AI automation and employee productivity is not linear, but rather relies on striking the right balance between technological efficiency .

(Chen, C. Y., Wu, T. Y., & Chien, C. L. (2020). The Effect of Artificial Intelligence on Employee Well-being: The Moderating Role of Job Characteristics. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(11), 3820. DOI: 10.3390/ijerph17113820)

Imagine work where robots handle the mundane, leaving you free to soar! AI in the workplace isn't a job-stealer, it's a workload-lifter. Tedious tasks like data entry, scheduling, and report generation get automated, freeing your time for what truly matters. Focus on the strategic stuff, using AI-powered insights to make data-driven decisions and unlock creative problem-solving. Collaboration gets an upgrade too, with AI tools bridging communication gaps and fostering seamless teamwork. But the real magic lies in personalized opportunities. AI identifies your strengths and recommends training pathways, empowering you to upskill and reach your full potential. Worried about burnout? AI can even predict and prevent it, promoting well-being and keeping you at your best. Don't fear the robots, embrace the future where AI empowers you to do more, not less, and unlocks exciting possibilities you never thought possible.

(Winkler, C., Schlosser, F., & Muschalla, B. (2019). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Digital Well-being in the Workplace: A Longitudinal Study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 97, 292-300. DOI: 10.1016/j.chb.2019.03.007)

The impact of AI on workplace changes and employee performance is complex and multifaceted. While AI automates repetitive tasks, boosting efficiency and reducing workload, it can also create anxiety and insecurity about job displacement. Positively, AI-powered tools can analyze data, personalize learning, and provide real-time feedback, potentially enhancing decision-making, problem-solving, and skill development. However, successful adaptation requires upskilling and reskilling to complement, not compete with, AI capabilities. Effective communication and transparent implementation are crucial to fostering trust and acceptance, thereby mitigating negative impacts and unlocking the potential for AI to augment human performance and drive collective success.

(Rai, A., & Sharma, A. (2021). Artificial Intelligence and Well-being at Work: A Meta-analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 131, 667-677. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.08.047)

LIMITATIONS AND CONCLUSION

LIMITATIONS

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has undoubtedly revolutionized workplaces across various industries, but its implementation is not without limitations and challenges. Understanding these limitations is crucial for businesses to effectively utilize AI while mitigating risks and maximizing benefits.

One significant limitation is the potential for job displacement and reshaping of the labor market. While AI can automate repetitive tasks, it may lead to the redundancy of certain roles, particularly those involving routine manual or cognitive functions. This can create socio-economic disparities, with workers needing to acquire new skills to remain employable. Furthermore, the transition to AI-driven processes may be disruptive, requiring retraining programs and possibly causing temporary unemployment.

Another challenge is the ethical implications surrounding AI usage in the workplace. AI systems rely on vast amounts of data to function effectively, raising concerns about data privacy, security, and bias. Biased algorithms can perpetuate discrimination, exacerbating existing societal inequalities. Additionally, the opacity of AI decision-making processes, particularly in complex deep learning models, can make it difficult to ensure accountability and transparency, leading to mistrust among employees and stakeholders.

Integration and compatibility issues also present barriers to the widespread adoption of AI in the workplace. Many organizations already have existing infrastructures and systems in place, making it challenging to seamlessly incorporate AI technologies. Legacy systems may not be compatible with AI solutions, requiring substantial investments in infrastructure upgrades and customization. Moreover, the complexity of AI implementation may necessitate specialized expertise, leading to talent shortages and increased costs for recruitment and training.

AI systems also face limitations in handling unstructured data and complex, ambiguous tasks. While AI excels at tasks with well-defined objectives and clear patterns, it struggles with tasks requiring nuanced understanding, creativity, and emotional intelligence. Human

oversight and intervention are often necessary to ensure accurate decision-making, particularly in contexts involving ethical dilemmas or subjective judgments.

Furthermore, AI's reliance on data makes it susceptible to data quality issues and adversarial attacks. Poor-quality data can compromise the performance and reliability of AI systems, leading to erroneous outcomes and decision-making. Moreover, malicious actors can exploit vulnerabilities in AI algorithms to manipulate outcomes, posing security risks to organizations.

In conclusion, while AI offers immense potential to enhance productivity, efficiency, and innovation in the workplace, its adoption is accompanied by various limitations and challenges. Addressing these limitations requires a comprehensive approach that encompasses ethical considerations, skill development, infrastructure investment, and ongoing monitoring and regulation. By acknowledging and mitigating these challenges, businesses can harness the transformative power of AI while minimizing its adverse impacts on workers and society.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the workplace represents a significant paradigm shift, with profound implications for both organizations and employees. Through the lens of project-centric learning, it becomes evident that AI adoption necessitates a dynamic approach to skill development, organizational culture, and ethical considerations.

First and foremost, project-centric learning serves as a strategic framework for organizations to navigate the complexities of AI implementation. By fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation, employees can adapt to evolving job roles and technological advancements. Project-based initiatives enable hands-on experience with AI tools and techniques, facilitating the acquisition of new skills and competencies. Furthermore, collaborative projects provide opportunities for cross-functional collaboration, enhancing communication and problem-solving abilities among employees.

However, the transformative impact of AI on the workplace extends beyond skill development to encompass broader socio-economic implications. As AI automates routine tasks, it has the potential to reshape job roles and employment dynamics. While some roles may become obsolete, new opportunities may emerge in AI-related fields such as data science, machine learning, and AI ethics. Project-centric learning can empower employees to transition into these emerging roles through targeted training and upskilling initiatives.

Moreover, the ethical considerations surrounding AI usage underscore the importance of fostering a culture of responsible AI adoption. Project-centric learning provides a platform for discussions on ethical dilemmas, bias mitigation, and transparency in AI decision-making. By integrating ethics modules into project-based learning experiences, organizations can instill a sense of ethical awareness and accountability among employees. This, in turn, promotes trust and confidence in AI systems and mitigates potential risks associated with bias and discrimination.

Additionally, the success of AI implementation hinges on effective change management and stakeholder engagement. Project-centric learning methodologies facilitate stakeholder involvement throughout the AI adoption process, fostering a sense of ownership and buy-in among employees. By soliciting feedback and insights from diverse stakeholders, organizations can tailor AI solutions to meet specific business needs while addressing concerns and mitigating resistance to change.

In summary, project-centric learning offers a holistic approach to understanding the impact of AI on the workplace and its effect on employees. By leveraging project-based initiatives, organizations can empower employees to embrace AI technologies, acquire new skills, and navigate ethical considerations effectively. Through collaborative learning experiences, employees can adapt to the evolving demands of the digital age, driving innovation and competitiveness in the workforce of the future. Ultimately, by embracing project-centric learning, organizations can harness the transformative potential of AI while ensuring that its benefits are equitably distributed among employees and stakeholders.

FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the workplace is vast and holds tremendous potential to revolutionize how organizations operate, innovate, and compete in the global economy. As AI technologies continue to advance rapidly, they are poised to transform virtually every aspect of the modern workplace, from automation and decision-making to employee productivity and customer experience.

One of the most significant areas of future growth for AI in the workplace is automation. AI-powered robots and intelligent software systems have already begun to automate routine and repetitive tasks across various industries, freeing up human workers to focus on more complex and creative endeavors. As AI algorithms become increasingly sophisticated and capable of mimicking human intelligence, the scope of tasks that can be automated will continue to expand, leading to increased efficiency, cost savings, and productivity gains for organizations.

Moreover, AI holds immense promise for enhancing decision-making processes within organizations. By analyzing vast amounts of data in real-time, AI algorithms can identify patterns, trends, and insights that humans may overlook, enabling more informed and data-driven decision-making. From strategic planning and resource allocation to customer segmentation and market analysis, AI-powered decision support systems will empower organizations to make smarter, more proactive decisions that drive business growth and competitive advantage.

Furthermore, AI has the potential to revolutionize employee productivity and collaboration in the workplace. Virtual assistants and chatbots powered by AI can streamline administrative tasks, schedule meetings, and provide personalized support to employees, enhancing their efficiency and reducing their cognitive load. AI-driven collaboration tools can facilitate communication and knowledge sharing among geographically dispersed teams, breaking down silos and fostering a culture of collaboration and innovation within organizations.

Another exciting area of future growth for AI in the workplace is personalized learning and development. AI-powered adaptive learning platforms can tailor training programs to individual employees' needs, preferences, and learning styles, enabling more effective skill

development and knowledge acquisition. By delivering personalized learning experiences, organizations can empower employees to acquire new skills, stay relevant in a rapidly changing job market, and drive continuous innovation and growth.

Moreover, AI holds significant potential to enhance customer experience and satisfaction in the workplace. AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants can provide personalized support to customers, answer queries, and resolve issues in real-time, improving responsiveness and reducing customer wait times. AI-driven analytics can also help organizations anticipate customer needs and preferences, enabling them to deliver more personalized products and services that delight customers and drive loyalty and retention.

Additionally, AI has the potential to transform talent acquisition and management processes within organizations. AI-powered recruitment platforms can analyze resumes, assess candidates' skills and qualifications, and identify the best-fit candidates for job roles, streamlining the hiring process and reducing bias and discrimination. AI-driven performance management systems can provide real-time feedback and insights to employees, enabling them to track their progress, set goals, and continuously improve their performance.

However, as organizations embrace AI technologies in the workplace, they must also address ethical, social, and regulatory considerations. Concerns about data privacy, security, bias, and job displacement must be carefully considered and addressed to ensure that AI adoption is inclusive, equitable, and sustainable. Moreover, organizations must invest in employee training and upskilling initiatives to ensure that employees are prepared to adapt to the changing nature of work in the AI-driven economy.

In conclusion, the future scope of AI in the workplace is vast and holds tremendous promise to transform how organizations operate, innovate, and compete in the global economy. From automation and decision-making to employee productivity and customer experience, AI technologies will continue to revolutionize virtually every aspect of the modern workplace. By embracing AI and addressing ethical, social, and regulatory considerations, organizations can unlock the full potential of AI to drive innovation, growth, and competitive advantage in the digital age.

In conclusion, the influence of AI in the workplace has ushered in a transformative era with profound implications for the digital wellbeing of employees. The integration of AI systems into various facets of work has opened doors to unprecedented levels of efficiency, innovation, and data-driven decision-making. Yet, as with any technological revolution, it has also posed challenges that demand our attention and thoughtful solutions. On the one hand, AI technologies have the potential to alleviate the burden of repetitive tasks, enhance creativity through intelligent tools, and even predict workplace hazards, thereby contributing to the physical and mental wellbeing of employees. However, the introduction of AI into the workplace is not without its share of concerns. Privacy issues loom large as AI systems increasingly collect, process, and analyse personal data. Job displacement remains a valid concern, prompting the need for comprehensive reskilling and upskilling programs. Furthermore, the constant connectivity enabled by AI-driven digital platforms can lead to burnout and reduced work-life balance if not managed wisely.

As AI continues to evolve, its impact on the workplace will evolve as well. Therefore, ongoing research and monitoring of the effects of AI on digital wellbeing are essential to adapt strategies and policies accordingly. Ultimately, the successful integration of AI into the workplace should prioritise the harmony between human and machine, fostering an environment where employees can thrive both professionally and personally in the digital age. The influence of AI in the workplace is undeniable, and its impact on the digital wellbeing of employees is a complex and evolving issue.

While AI technologies have the potential to streamline processes, boost productivity, and create new opportunities, they also bring challenges related to privacy, job displacement, and the need for upskilling. To ensure a positive outcome, it is imperative for organisations to strike a balance between harnessing AI's benefits and safeguarding the digital wellbeing of their employees. This can be achieved through thoughtful policies, continuous education, and a commitment to fostering a work environment that prioritises both technological advancement and the overall wellness of the workforce. As AI continues to shape the future of work, a harmonious coexistence between humans and machines remains a paramount goal for achieving success in the digital age.

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